

Drowning in the Weight of Your Expectations

(Score and Documentation)

Sophie Rose

Table of Contents

OUTLINE	2
PERFORMANCE GESTURE ROUTING TABLE	3
TEXT	4
MAX ROUTINGS (VERSION 4 OF GLVD, SELF-BUILT GLOVES)	5
TOP LEFT	5
BOTTOM LEFT.....	6
TOP RIGHT.....	7
BOTTOM RIGHT	8
PROJECTIONS	9
STAGE AUDIO CONFIGURATION	10

Outline

Duration: 6 minutes 0 seconds

Released on Fair_Play's album "Inclusives": 14/05/2021

<https://fairplaynetwork.bandcamp.com/album/inclusives>

<https://open.spotify.com/track/2it02fLJU4KBXB9ybd2Hi0?si=66988692608c400f>

This is a fixed media, audiovisual work. This piece was written in collaboration with the French feminist collective Fair_Play. Four artists (Sage Pbbbt, Zineb Soulaïmani, Laryssa Kim, and Carol Robinson) created banks of sounds and enlisted up to 10 other female and non-binary artist-composers each. Those roughly 40 artists were given all four banks of sounds and allowed free reign for up to six minutes. I used small parts of the content provided and my voice as material for gestural manipulation.

I used *GLVD (version four)* to create several layers from the donated samples and manipulate a line of spoken text (additional to the supplied material). The text and samples are curated around Fair_Play's mission to give women, non-binary, and gender-diverse artists a platform to balance the male-dominated composition field. I used gestural manipulation to control delay and granular synthesis on the spoken text's main line, grabbing snatches of the text as it was delivered and manipulating it in real time. The low-frequency, underwater whoomph's central layer was created through live triggering and destructively editing small fragments of three artists using *Wave* (Genki Instruments 2019). I repeated this destructive process several times to create layers. I used the clarinet playing of one artist, filtered out the low frequencies, and used this to mirror the bird and nature sounds that faded over the last half of the piece. This incorporates some of my interest in animism and urban shamanism with one of the collaborators, Sage Pbbbt's, intimate involvement and practice with urban shamanism and chaos magick by mirroring the natural through various human-made constructions and confines (Harlow 2019).

Music and video by Sophie Rose.

Performance Gesture Routing Table

These routings cover one of the layers and show an example of how controls were routed to effects.

Controls were reused multiple times to create different layers of audio.

NAME Drowning in the Weight of Your Expectations		
Gesture	CC/Note	Routing
Genki Wave		
R Roll	CC 1/16	Track 19: Granulator II, Grain Size 150Hz – 0.25Hz
	CC 1/17	Track 19: Granulator II, File Position 0.0 – 100.0
R Open + Wrist Flick	CC 1/18	Track 19: Granulator II, Spray 0.0ms – 20.0s
L Fist + Pitch	CC 1/21	Track 19: Granulator II, Grab
GLVD		
L Yaw	CC 1/1	Track 2: Erosion, Frequency 18Khz – 300Hz Track 2: Grain Delay, Pitch -36.0 – 12.0 Track 3: MHarmonizerMB, Shift > Shift 1 0 – 1
L Pitch	CC 1/2	Track 2: Grain Delay, Frequency 1.0Hz – 150Hz Track 3: MHarmonizerMB, Shift > Shift 2 0 – 1
L Roll	CC 1/4	Track 2: Grain Delay, Spray 0.00ms – 500ms
R Yaw	CC 1/6	Track 6: MHarmonizerMB, Shift > Shift 1 0 – 1
R Pitch	CC 1/7	Track 6: MHarmonizerMB, Shift > Shift 3 0 – 1 Track 6: OVox Resynthesis (m>s), Note Mapper Root
L Fist + Roll	ON 1/33	Track 2: Looper, Stop
R Fist + Pitch	ON 1/35	Track 3: Looper, Stop
R Fist + Roll	ON 1/37	Track 3: Looper, Play
L Open + Wrist Flick	ON 1/39	Track 6: Looper, Reverse
L Puppet + Yaw	ON 1/41	Track 3: Looper, Reverse
L Puppet + Pitch	ON 1/53	Track 6: Looper, Play
R Puppet + Yaw	ON 1/54	Track 6: Looper, Stop
R Puppet + Pitch	ON 1/32	Track 2: Looper, Play

Text

I've always felt like I'm drowning in expectations. When I try to make myself heard, I'm just simply too emotional, and I'm unstable. I'm just damaged, and I'm irrational.

If I tell you my experiences, I'm just an outlier. One bad experience among so many good ones. So many good ones...

I'm exaggerating. I'm too sensitive.

If I quote facts, or statistics, or papers? Then I'm being elitist, and I'm stuck up. And I can't be trusted because I was wrong once in the past.

I get maybe five seconds to impress you with some sort of profoundness, with acumen, some sort of shred of shrewdness. If I miss my mark – or if I misspeak, heaven forbid... If I'm inarticulate from lack of practice expressing my ideas out loud... well then... of course! I'm nothing.

My knowledge is nothing.

My voice? Nothing.

My brain?

Nothing.

Certainly, in canon, my body is absolutely nothing.

If I tell you my wants, I'm just too needy. Or, if I tell you my wants, and my desires, and my goals, then I'm too young to know. Sometimes I even ask too much.

It's always too much.

Max Routings (Version 4 of GLVD, self-built gloves)

This screenshot has been broken up into four parts. This is the LEFT HAND only, the right is a duplicate of this configuration.

Top Left

Figure 1. The top left portion of the screen from max-patch for *Drowning in the Weight of Your Expectations*.

Bottom Left

Figure 2. The bottom left portion of the screen from max-patch for *Drowning in the Weight of Your Expectations*.

Top Right

Figure 3. The top right portion of the screen from max-patch for *Drowning in the Weight of Your Expectations*.

Bottom Right

Figure 4. The bottom right portion of the screen from max-patch for *Drowning in the Weight of Your Expectations*.

Projections

The video component for this work was designed around women’s use of make-up as a subversive social tool. This “war paint” is a façade to engage with society, covering the true face to present a more appealing and acceptably feminine one (Loegel et al. 2017; Ghafaryanshirazi 2016; Ogilvie 2005; Cash and Cash 1982; Ogilvie and Ryan 2011). The face becomes art – no imperfections, only featureless and silent beauty. I paint my face and neck entirely white using cheap foundation, see **Figure 5**, to visually reference milky marble used in Western sculpture¹. The stark, appliance-white face staring dispassionately mimics these unblinking marble statues that are so revered. The tri-colour prism split alludes to media’s role in reinforcing misogynistic attitudes (Altay 2014; McLaren 2019; McRobbie 2020).

Figure 5. Still image from *Drowning’s* video showing tri-colour effect and final painted face.

¹ Even though our “white” statues were initially painted in bright colours (Talbot 2018).

Stage Audio Configuration

S.1, S.2, et cetera are speakers.

Figure 6. Image showing the speaker layout for March 2023 performances at Three Phase Rehearsal Studios, Brunswick, VIC, AU. Channels are standard configuration, 1-2 (Screen left/right), 3-4 (middle left/right), and 5-6 (back by projector left/right).